

Table 1. Aspartate kinase (AK) (nkat mg prot⁻¹) and Homoserine dehydrogenase (HSDH) (nmol min⁻¹ mg prot⁻¹) activities extracted from developing seeds of rice.

Enzyme/treatment	Developing seeds		
	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3
AK			
Control	0.046	0.070	0.055
+Thr	0.044	0.061	0.052
+Lys	0.004	0.036	0.042
+Lys + Thr	0.003	0.025	0.040
HSDH			
Control	1.389	0.704	0
+Thr	0.849	0.610	0

Table 2. Lysine ketoglutarate (LKR) and saccharopine dehydrogenase (SDH) activities (nmol min⁻¹ mg prot⁻¹) extracted from rice and soybean tissues.

Plant tissue	LKR activity	SDH activity
<i>Rice</i>		
Developing seeds (stage 1)	4.6	5.0
Developing seeds (stage 2)	9.1	4.2
Developing seeds (stage 3)	0	2.0
Root	0	0
Leaf	0	0
<i>Soybean</i>		
Cotyledons	0.24	1.06
Developing seeds	5.10	3.16

studied so far (Lea et al 1992), with the exception of *Coix lacryma-jobi*.

It is currently difficult to assure that an isoenzyme sensitive to Thr is present in rice seeds. For HSDH, we did not observe a Thr-sensitive form of the enzyme, as isolated in other plant species studied. These results suggest that a bifunctional enzyme containing Tht-sensitive AK-HSDH activities, such as the enzyme isolated from some higher plants (Azevedo et al 1992b), is not present in rice.

LKR and SDH were extracted from rice and soybean tissues using phosphate and Tris buffers. The inclusion of PVP is essential to maintain both activities independent of the buffer system used. The presence of KC1 at 50 mM also helped to maintain the activity. LKR and SDH activities were observed in developing seeds at three different stages. However, LKR and SDH activities were not present in roots and leaves (Table 2). In soybean, both LKR and SDH activities were observed in developing seeds and cotyledons (Table 2).

These preliminary tests showed that both enzymes are very sensitive to proteases and phenolic compounds during extraction. High concentration of salts in the buffer also appears to increase enzyme activity. The evidence suggests that both enzymes are seed-specific in rice but not in soybean.

Cited references

- Azevedo RA, Blackwell RD, Smith RJ, Lea PJ. 1992a. Three aspartate kinase isoenzymes from maize. *Phytochemistry* 31:3725-3730.
- Azevedo RA, Smith RJ, Lea PJ. 1992b. Aspartate kinase regulation in maize:

evidence for co-purification of threonine-sensitive aspartate kinase and homoserine dehydrogenase. *Phytochemistry* 31:3731-3734.

- Brochetto-Braga M, Leite A, Arruda P. 1992. Partial purification and characterization of lysine-ketoglutarate reductase in normal and opaque-2 maize endosperms. *Plant Physiol.* 98:1139-1147.
- Lea PJ, Blackwell RD, Azevedo RA. 1992. Analysis of barley metabolism using mutant genes. In: Shewry PR, editor. *Barley: genetics, molecular biology and biotechnology*. Oxford: CAB International. p 181-208. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Use of genetic male sterile-facilitated recurrent selection for blast resistance in rice

B. N. Singh, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA) Rice Program, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan Nigeria; T. M. Masajo, IRRI, Antananarivo, Madagascar; and O. A. Oladimeji, WARDA Rice Program, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria

Rice blast (*Pyricularia grisea*) is a serious disease in rainfed, upland, and lowland ecologies in Africa. Many blast races are rapidly changing (Awoderu 1970, Fomba and Taylor, 1994). Breeding resistant varieties by combining genes from various sources is one of the most efficient and cost-effective approaches for blast management. We used genetic male sterile lines to incorporate genes from various improved donors.

In 1984 wet season, 18 crosses were initially made by hand pollination between 6 genetic male sterile lines from IRRI and 11 improved donors that are irrigated and rainfed lowland plant types with resistance to blast and tolerance for iron toxicity (see table). The male sterile lines have intermediate height and medium growth duration except for IR36, which is semi-dwarf and early-maturing. From the F₂ and subsequent generations, the seeds from male sterile plants were harvested after random mating. In each cycle, the population was subjected to natural blast infestation.

In the third cycle, crosses were also made with eight new lines with improved plant type (see table). After five cycles of random mating, selections were made for male fertile recombinants and grown using the pedigree method. Lines were further screened for leaf blast resistance under spreader row inoculation method. Three to

Male sterile lines and fertile donors used in the study.

Male sterile lines	Male fertile donors ^a	Male fertile donors ^b
IR36 (ms)	ITA121	BKNFR76106-16-0-1-0
IR41512	ITA212	IR24637-38-2-21
IR41519	ITA230	ITA230
IR41523	PELITA 1-1	ITA315
IR41525	TOX906-92-20-1-1-1	Mat Candu
IR41530	TOX725-1-8-20-1	TOX3058-28-1-1-1
	ITA245	TOX3118-2-E2-2-3
	Suakoko 8	TOX3219-24-1-3
	ITA247	
	Mahsuri	
	ITA231	

^aInitial crosses made in 1984. ^bCrosses made in third cycle.

Frequency distribution of 568 lines for their reactions to leaf blast.

six plants were selected from each segregating line.

The 27 fixed lines with blast resistance were evaluated for yield in 1994 wet season. Leaf blast resistance of 568 lines generated through genetic male sterile-facilitated recurrent selection (GMSFRS) were evaluated in a greenhouse under upland direct seeded condition during the 1994 wet season (August-October). The spreader row consisted of mixed seed of three highly susceptible lines: OB677, TOX3055-10-1-1-1-1 (TOX3055), and ITA306. The test entries (10 g each) were seeded in single, 50 cm-rows, 16 d later. Twenty days after seeding, the spreader rows were inoculated with mixed field isolates of leafblast at ITTA. Rainfall was favorable for disease development. Five checks—IR46, ITA212, ITA305, TOX3055, and ITA306—were randomly planted in each 10th row to monitor variation in leaf blast infection. The susceptible checks, such as OB677, TOX3055, and ITA306, had developed the susceptible lesions and more than 50% diseased leaf area (DLA) by 14 d. Leaf

blast infection was recorded from 14 to 42 d after inoculation at weekly intervals for both lesion type and % DLA using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (IRRI 1988).

We classified the 568 pedigree lines derived from the interbreeding composite population into four groups:

- Group I : Immune type: no lesion development, true or complete resistance.
- Group II: Moderately resistant type: initially resistant, and the disease developed to a score of 2 or 3 and up to 5% DLA (ITA305).
- Group III : Partial or field resistant type: initially resistant to moderately resistant, and the disease developed to a major lesion type score of 4 or 5 (moderately susceptible) and from 6 to 25% DLA.
- Group IV: Susceptible type: initial reaction was resistant, moderately resistant (IR46), or moderately susceptible (TOX3055, ITA306, or ITA212), and the disease score ranged from 7 (susceptible) to 9 (highly susceptible) and DLA was 26-100%.

Thirty percent of the lines were classified as highly resistant (group I), another 22% were moderately resistant (group II), 33% were partially resistant, and 25% susceptible to highly susceptible. Among partially resistant types, 12% were initially highly resistant (I, IIIii). Among susceptible types, 4% were initially resistant (IV-i), 16% had moderate resistance (IV-iii), and another 5% had a moderately susceptible reaction (IV-iii). The frequency distribution shows that 85% of the lines had blast resistance incorporated through GMSFRS (see figure). Variation was observed in the DLA of five checks. To evaluate the elite lines, the entries need to be replicated. Three highly susceptible lines and broad-based field isolates will be used to inoculate the spreader rows when selecting lines with horizontal resistance.

In GMSFRS, the parent identity is lost to random mating and a composite population of lines is generated in each cycle. Male sterile-facilitated recurrent selection has been used in barley to develop composites (Jensen 1988). Genetic male sterile lines were effectively used to develop interbreeding composite populations for incorporating the genes for blast resistance from various improved donors. We are evaluating many resistant lines with rainfed and irrigated lowland plant type for their yield potential and resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses.

Cited references

- Awoderu VA. 1970. Identification of races of *Pyricularia oryzae* in Nigeria. *Plant Dis. Rep.* 54:520-523.
- Romba SN, Taylor DR. 1994. Rice blast in West Africa: its nature and control In: Zeigler RS, Leong SA, Teng PS, editors. *Rice blast disease*. UK: CAB International. p 343-355.
- [IRRI] International Rice Research Institute 1998. *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Manila (Philippines): IRRI. 54 p.
- Jensen NF. 1988. Male sterile facilitated recurrent selection method. In: *Plant breeding methodology*. New York: John Wiley & Sons. p 243-248. ■